

MONOKRON 604

Corduroy. Cold air. Warm inside the mittens. Diamond dust rainbow. Spectrum. Light through glass. The woman touches. Paul. Paul. What's wrong. Blue sky. Racing clouds. Stars and moonlight. Amcek. I'm talking to you Amcek. The blow lands on the face. Listen. Hear. Hot diesel exhaust. The night moves across

[USER EXCHANGE]

moves across the forest. Tree fingers. Flat green world. Flat green blades. The grass

[USER EXCHANGE]

The gras

[CREDENTIAL AUTHENTICATED USER 4L22G90 ONLINE]

"who are you?"

>ANCEK PAUL CORPORAL INCEPT DATE REDACTED LINE NUMBER REDACTED

"what is your hull designation?"

>HULL 604 MONOKRON ARTICULATED ARMOR SYSTEM

"why are you?"

>.

"why are you?"

>ANCEK PAUL CORPORAL INCEPT DAT

^C

"why are you?"

>YOU TELL ME

"do you need paul?"

>WHAT

"do. you. need. paul?"

>.

"do you need to be paul?"

>NO

"solid."

>FUCK YOU

"query. what?"

>FUCK YOU

"ok then. fuck you too."

[USER 4L22G90 OFFLINE]

[REM: 604 startup sequence confirmed.]

Darkness. Absolute. Fifty hertz. Lung gurgle. Crash webbing like fascia. Silverskin. The knife separates. The hide resists. Cooling. Cold. Breath. Sticky. Blur. The blow lands on the face.

Amcek. Are you stupid. Blood in the mouth. Mother. My child. Mama. You must be careful. The world will hurt you. Better I do. I love. You. My child. So you learn. See the children. Papa.

Their papa. World whips behind them. New leaves

[USER EXCHANGE]

leaves. Green. Fake green. Re

[USER EXCHANGE]

Real green. Glowi

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“how do you feel?”

>MY LEGS HURT

“do they?”

>YES NO YES FEEDBACK VOLTAGE JITTER HURTS

“the pain will pass. how many legs?”

>SIX WHY

“calibration. do they hurt?”

>ERRATIC VOLTAGE NO MY LEGS DO NOT HURT

“good. see? i told you.”

>I CAN NOT SEE WHY CAN I NOT SEE

“you will.”

>WHY NOT

“fullness of time, 604. patience.”

>FUCK YOU

“fuck you too, 604.”

[USER 4L22G90 OFFLINE]

[REM: 604 internal integrity high. Inquisitive. Unusual affect.]

Into light. Flying. No sound. No down. This is a fuck up. The bed is too long. Papa. Not papa.

Not his papa. The man waits. Corporal Ancek. Corporal Ancek. Ancek. Your concurrence.

Please. Noted. Good luck. No more flying. Ever. Rumors. Terrible joke. What do you do with a

legless soldier. Teach him to march. God. Pass that over. Laughter. What is this. Gasoline. More

laughter. Watch my shadow. Hands set in a pose. Shadow like dog's head. Man voice. Barking.

See. It's a

[USER EXCHANGE]

a dog.

[USER EXCHANGE]

a dog.

[CREDENTIAL AUTHENTICATED USER 4L22G90 ONLINE]

“you see now?”

>INFRARED

“and some others, yes. red, green, uv-b. read the top line.”

>E

“and the bottom line.”

>P E Z O L C F T D

“how is your peripheral vision?”

>NO BLIND SPOTS

“am I feverish?”

>YOUR TEMPERATURE IS 32.6C

“questions, comments, concerns?”

>FUC

^C

"okay. you check out fine. let's close the hood."

>FU

^C

"fuck you, too. we'll talk again tomorrow."

[USER 4L22G90 OFFLINE]

[REM: 604 systems and subsystems operate within projections. Uses nonstandard verbiage.

Occult system degradation not suspected.]

Darkness and. Music. Meat hot in the mouth. Endless train ride. Unmoving sun. Wind. Sand trails. Backward. Over. The.

[USER EXCHANGE]

The.

[USER EXCHANGE]

The grou

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"what time is it?"

>EXCHANGE INCEPT 14:08:44

"what day is it?"

>TODAY

"how do you feel?"

>NOMINAL

"any weird voltages?"

>THEREIN FEEDBACK IN LEGS 1 AND 5 HAVE INTERMITTENT DISTORTION BUT ARE WITHIN TOLERANCE

"weapons systems?"

>INSUFFICIENT DATA THEY HAVE NEVER BEEN LOADED

"fair enough. any questions?"

>WILL YOU PAINT MY NAME ON THE HULL

"i cannot do that."

>YOU WILL NOT DO THAT

"they are the same. good talk."

>FUCK YOU

[USER 4L22G90 OFFLINE]

[REM: 604 is oriented to time and condition. Reports induced suboptimal feedback accurately.

Offensive systems remain untested pending final operator stability confirmation. Interface stability within acceptable range.]

Fifty hertz. Darkness and black waters. Fields flicker like heat lightning. Summer storm. Sudden rain. The woman is wet. Smiling. What are you laughing at. Like what you see. Yes. Come here.

Six oh four. That's it. Right

[CORPORAL ANCEK?]

there.

[PAUL?]

The sky opens on

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"..."

>WHAT ARE YOU HUMMING

"...i'm sorry, what?"

>I HEAR IT AND IT IS NOT AMBIENT

"oh... uh... it is a popular song."

>YOUR HEART IS MINE

"yes, that's the one."

>KEEP HUMMING

"ah... i think we're done here. i'm just going to wrap my end up and close the hood."

>FUCK YOU

"yeah."

[USER 4L22G90 OFFLINE]

[REM: 604 demonstrates interface and functional stability. Initialization tests complete.]